

Spectrophotometric Determination of Gold using *N*-Methylanilinecarbodithioate as a Reagent

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THERE are various reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of gold¹. In most of the cases, the sensitivity is low and the color fades after some time, while in some the complex is formed either slowly or on heating for a long time. Xanthates have also been used as extraction reagents, however, the stability and sensitivity are low because the gold complexes are not extracted completely². In this work *N*-methylanilinecarbodithioate has been used as a reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of gold by adsorption of its complex onto microcrystalline naphthalene. The method is more convenient as it is carried out at room temperature, rapid economical (only 0.4 g of naphthalene is required), sensitive and can be applied to various kind of minerals and alloys.

Experimental

A digital pH meter and a SP-20 Spectronic spectrophotometer were used. All solvents and reagents were of analytical reagent grade.

Gold solution (10^{-2} M) was prepared in hydrochloric acid and diluted to a 1 M with respect to acid solution. Sodium *N*-methylanilinecarbodithioate was prepared by the reported method³. A 0.2% solution of the reagent was prepared in distilled water and standardised titrimetrically using mercury(II) acetate as titrant and diphenylcarbazone as an internal indicator.

Procedure: To gold solution (40 ml) containing 49.8 μ g of gold was added the reagent solution (0.2%; 2 ml) and pH of the solution was adjusted to 2.0–4.0 with perchloric acid and ammonia solutions. The solution was allowed to stand for 2 min and then 20% naphthalene solution (2 ml) was added and shaken vigorously for 1 min. The resulting solid was dissolved in dimethylformamide and diluted to 10 ml. A portion of this solution was taken and absorbance was measured at 380 nm against the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of gold-dithiocarbamate complex was recorded in dimethylformamide against the reagent blank. The complex absorbs strongly at 380 nm. Maximum absorbance was observed when the pH of the aqueous phase was 2.0–4.5 and when 1.0–4.0 ml of the reagent was used. The complex was coprecipitated quantitatively when

1.0–4.0 ml of 20% naphthalene was used and when the volume of the aqueous phase was less than 50 ml. Hence for convenient handling 40 ml of aqueous phase and 2.0 ml of 20% naphthalene were used. Results were found to be quantitative in the presence of 0.05–0.1 M of the sodium perchlorate concentration in the aqueous phase. The absorbance of the complex remained practically constant for more than 6 h.

The calibration graph obtained under the optimum conditions was linear over the concentration range 15–120 μ g of gold in 10 ml of final solution. The molar absorptivity and the relative standard deviation for 49.8 μ g were found to be 4.94×10^4 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 1.6%, respectively.

The composition of the complex was studied by Job's method of continuous variation and mole-ratio method. A sharp peak at 0.25 mol fraction and a break at 1 : 3 mole ratio (metal-ligand) suggested the adsorption of Au(N-CH₃C₆H₅CS₂)₃ under these conditions.

Sample solutions containing 49.8 μ g of gold and various amounts of different anions as alkali metal salts or metal ions were prepared and the general procedure was applied. The following ions (amount shown in parenthesis) did not interfere: acetate, nitrate, fluoride, bromide, iodide, oxalate, phosphate, carbonate, sulphate, thiocyanate, chloride and nitrite (100 mg each); citrate (45 mg); EDTA (40 mg); Pb^{II}, Zn^{II}, Co^{II}, As^{III}, Fe^{III}, Fe^{II}, Te^{IV}, Si^{IV}, Pt^{IV}, Os^{VII}, Cr^{III}, (2 mg each); Ca^{II}, Al^{III}, Mg^{II} (4 mg each); Mo^{VI} (0.2 mg). The interference of copper and nickel was eliminated by using 2.0 ml of 5% KCN.

Gold in synthetic mixtures: Appropriate amount of various metal salts were mixed in such a way that the final composition of the mixture corresponded to the standard alloys/minerals. To the mixture (1.0 g) corresponding to the minerals and alloy, was added aqua-regia (10 ml), and the mixture was heated gently to dissolve it completely. Then concentrated HCl (15 ml) was added in steps of 2 ml each. The solution was then evaporated on a boiling water-bath to dryness. The residue was dissolved in 1 M HCl (10 ml), diluted with distilled water and

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF GOLD IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Alloy Mineral	Gold taken* μ g	Gold found* μ g	Relative standard deviation %
Propezite	20.5	21.5	0.80
	38.0	38.9	0.69
	52.9	53.1	1.18
Sylvanite	33.5	33.3	1.42
	45.0	45.7	0.88
	50.1	50.6	0.86
Au - Pd alloy	25.0	25.9	0.74
	40.0	40.9	0.94
	70.0	70.7	0.85

* Average of five determinations.

filtered if silver was present in the sample and diluted to 500 ml with distilled water. To an aliquot of the sample solution, EDTA (1% ; 0.5 ml) and KCN (2% ; 2 ml) were added in order to eliminate the interference of lead, copper and nickel. The determination of gold(III) was then carried out by the general procedure. The results of the determinations are given in Table I.

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